

EFFECTIVENESS OF EXISTING ORGANIZATIONAL-LEGAL AND FINANCIAL-ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR SUPPORTING THE EXPORT OF ICT SERVICES

Shermatov Sherzod Khotamovich

Minister of Digital Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan

sherzod.shermatov@gmail.com

Abstract: The effectiveness of existing organizational, legal, and financial-economic mechanisms for supporting the export of ICT services has been analyzed. Ecosystems contributing to the development of IT services exports, methods for training qualified personnel, strengthening international cooperation, the production of high-value-added products, and infrastructure development have been studied in depth. Practical proposals aimed at strengthening regulatory, legal, and financial support were also developed.

Keywords: *Export of IT services, ICT services, financial and economic mechanisms, organizational and legal factors, financial and economic factors, expansion of exports of IT services.*

AKT XIZMATLARI EKSPORTINI QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING MAVJUD TASHKILY-HUQUQIY VA MOLIYAVIY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARI SAMARADORLIGI

Shermatov Sherzod Xotamovich

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi raqamli texnologiyalar vaziri

sherzod.shermatov@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: AKT xizmatlari eksportini qo‘llab-quvvatlashga oid mavjud tashkiliy-huquqiy hamda moliyaviy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarning samaradorligi tahlil qilingan. IT xizmatlar eksportini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiluvchi ekotizimlar, malakali kadrlar tayyorlash yo‘llari, xalqaro hamkorlikni kuchaytirish, yuqori qo‘shilgan

qimmatli mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish hamda infratuzilmani rivojlantirish masalalari chuqur o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, normativ-huquqiy va moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashni kuchaytirishga qaratilgan amaliy takliflar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *IT xizmatlar eksporti, AKT xizmatlari, moliyaviy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlar, Tashkiliy- huquqiy omillar, Moliyaviy- iqtisodiy omillar, IT-xizmatlar eksportini kengaytirish.*

The effectiveness of existing organizational, legal, and financial-economic mechanisms for supporting the export of ICT services is clearly demonstrated by international experience. In particular, through the development of service exports, the total volume of exports in countries with a large population, such as India and China, increased, which had a positive impact on improving the well-being of the population. In particular, the ICT sector and the digital economy in India have become one of the main drivers of the country's economy, accounting for more than 13 percent of GDP.

At the same time, many scientific studies have been conducted in the CIS and other foreign countries on expanding the activities of organizational and financial instruments in improving the export of ICT services, especially the development of ecosystems that serve to increase the export of IT services. The development of the export of IT services is one of the priorities of the country's economic policy, and the experience of developed countries shows that this process is carried out not only by restricting imports, but also by increasing the efficiency of IT export activities.

Meanwhile, the process of globalization is accelerating the digitalization of the economy through ICT services and expanding opportunities to increase GDP. The export of information technology-based services is consistently developing from year to year. The organization of IT services requires less costs than production, and it is possible to implement them through the Internet. Therefore, in countries that have effectively utilized these factors, new jobs are being created and youth employment is

ensured through ICT services. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4337 dated May 24, 2019, “On measures to expand mechanisms for financing and insurance protection of export activities.”¹

The following measures are important in the development of ICT services in this direction:

1. *Training qualified personnel:* Training specialists with modern knowledge and skills in the field of ICT and adapting them to the requirements of international markets serves to improve the quality of services.

2. *Applying innovative solutions:* Supporting startups and IT companies and financing their innovative projects will expand opportunities for implementing new technologies.

3. *Strengthening international cooperation:* Developing partnerships with international technology centers and markets increases export potential and enables access to new markets.

4. *Infrastructure development:* Improving digital infrastructure, including the development of high-speed internet, cloud technologies, and data centers, will increase the efficiency of ICT services.

5. *Regulatory and financial support:* ICT exports can be developed through improving the legal framework, tax incentives, and financial incentives. This makes Uzbekistan one of the leaders in the region in the export of ICT services.

This will contribute not only to economic growth but also to strengthening the country's position on the global technological map.

As a result, new jobs will be created by developing the export of ICT services, especially youth employment will be ensured, and sustainable sources of economic growth will be formed.

One of the global problems in the world is poverty, and in the last 20 years, many measures have been taken to get out of poverty. One of these measures is to create more vacancies at a lower cost. The creation and sale of ICT services through information technology to provide employment for the population is one of the trending topics of

¹ <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-4351732?ONDATE=12.12.2019%2000>

recent years. The problem of ensuring the employment of the world's population is one of the major problems, and various ways to solve this problem are being sought, especially in high-population countries, and the found solutions are being implemented in practice.

Figure 1. Existing organizational, legal, and financial-economic mechanisms for supporting the export of ICT services are the main

factors²

One of the easiest ways to escape poverty is to increase the income of the population by using human intelligence and selling services created by human intelligence. According to statista.com, a popular website in the USA, the share of the world's population living in poverty has been decreasing from the 1990s to 2022. The fact that one of the modern services contributing to poverty reduction is the improvement of the creation of IT services is scientifically substantiated by Janet A. Dzator, an economist at the University of Newcastle, in her article “Using Digital Technologies for Development: Does ICT Contribute to Poverty Reduction.”

Einar H. Dyvik, a specialist in research covering global data for Scandinavia and society, economics, and politics, noted in his research that one of the measures related to ensuring employment and increasing public income in countries is the development of science in the country and the expansion of products and services created through information and communication technologies (ICT).

In recent decades, global economic growth has been primarily driven by technological acceleration and the growing demand for information and communication technology (ICT) products and services. These processes have led the export of ICT services to leading positions in the global market system. However, employment in the ICT sector did not expand at the same rate. This imbalance can be explained by the shift in specialization in ICT sectors from production to service exports, as well as the varying degree of effectiveness of the organizational, legal, and financial-economic mechanisms used in this process. Over the past five years, Uzbekistan has carried out extensive work aimed at creating favorable conditions for the formation and active development of high-tech sectors of the economy based on the use of ICT, further deepening the integration of science, education, and production in this sector by providing additional benefits and

² Muallif ishlanmasi

preferences to manufacturers and customers of information technology products, increasing the export of ICT products, and stimulating the attraction of domestic and foreign investment.

Conclusion. International experience in supporting the export of ICT services shows that effective organizational, legal, and financial mechanisms increase economic growth and prosperity. In the case of India and China, the ICT sector has made a significant contribution to GDP and employment growth. This sector creates high value at low cost and provides employment for young people. Human resources, innovation, infrastructure, and incentive systems are important factors for development. In general, ICT exports contribute to economic growth, poverty reduction, and strengthening the digital economy.

List of references

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4337 dated May 24, 2019, "On measures to expand mechanisms for financing and insurance protection of export activities."
2. Ronen, Eyal, ICT Services Export and Labour Demand: Global Perspective and the Case of Israel (February 24, 2021). Skills Transformation for a Changing World: Understanding Skills Requirements in EU Neighboring Countries. European Foundation for Education. ed.
3. Engineering and Economics, 3 (1), 7-13. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837541>.
4. Jumaboev Akmaljon Sheralievich. (2025). Improving the financial support for the export of IT services.
5. Karimov, B. (2021). "Export Development in the IT Sector: Theory and Practice." Journal of Economics and Education, 7 (2), 58–70.
6. Zhiyamuratov Rustam Nuridinovich (2025). Foreign trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan: key indicators and development trends. Journal of marketing, business and management, 4 (4), 92-96.
7. Yusupov, A. (2022). "Issues of improving the financial support for the export of IT services in Uzbekistan." Journal of Finance and Investment, 4 (10), 45-56.